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Direct Infusion Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study				Platelet lipidomics indicates enhanced thrombocyte activation in APS in vivo (FIA-FTMS)			
Document creation date		07/30/2024		Corresponding Email		Marcus.Hoering@ukr.de	
Principal investigator		Marcus Höring		Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?		Untargeted	
Institution		Institute of Clinical Chemistry and Laboratory Medicine, University Hospital Regensburg		Clinical		Yes	

Lipid extraction

Extraction method		2-phase system		Were internal standards added prior extraction?		Yes	
pH adjustment		None		Special conditions		-	
2-phase system		Bligh&Dyer		Derivatization		-	

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium formate	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS1	3
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Recording mode of raw data at MS1	Profile mode
MS type	Orbitrap	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1
MS vendor	Thermo	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	High resolution
Direct type	FIA	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS2	140.000
MS Level	MS1, MS2	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS2	3
Mass resolution for detected ion at MS1	High resolution	Recording mode of raw data at MS2	Profile mode
Resolution at m/z 200 at MS1	140.000	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Solvent blank, Internal standard blank	Type of QC sample	Sample pool

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Precision	Yes
Lipid recovery	Yes	Accuracy	Yes
Dynamic quantification range	No	Guidelines followed	None
Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	Yes		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Available on request	Raw data upload	Available on request
Are metadata available?	Available on request	Additional comments	-

Sample Descriptions

Platelets, activated platelets and lipid release / Human / Cells

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage time (month)	18
Provided preanalytical information	Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Freeze-thaw cycles	1
Temperature handling original sample	Room temperature	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	180	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	ALEX
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

1) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Accuracy and coefficient of variation (< 20 %)
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
TG 51:0	TG		
TG 57:0	TG		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Reported data quantified with TG 51:0
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

2) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CE	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	ALEX
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	-

2) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Accuracy and coefficient of variation (< 20 %)
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
CE 17:0	CE		
CE 22:0	CE		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	Response model	Further quantification remarks	Reported data quantified with CE 17:0
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

3) PC[M+HCOO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Which assumptions were presumed?	Only even chain fatty acyl chains
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+HCOO]-	Lipid Identification Software	ALEX
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	Confirmation by positive ion mode and MS2
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

3) PC[M+HCOO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Accuracy and coefficient of variation (< 20 %)
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PC 28:0	PC		
PC 44:0	PC		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Reported data quantified with PC 28:0
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

4) SM[M+HCOO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SM	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+HCOO]-	Lipid Identification Software	ALEX
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	Confirmation by MS2 on a triple-quadrupole

4) SM[M+HCOO]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Accuracy and coefficient of variation (< 20 %)
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
SM 18:1;O2/12:0	SM		
SM 18:1;O2/18:1[D9]	SM		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Reported data quantified with SM 18:1;O2/18:1[D9]
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

5) PC O[M+HCOO]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC O	Which assumptions were presumed?	Only even chain fatty acyl chains
MS Level for identification	MS1	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Negative	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+HCOO] ⁻	Lipid Identification Software	ALEX
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
Background check at MS1	Yes	Further identification remarks	Confirmation by positive ion mode and MS2
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

5) PC O[M+HCOO]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Accuracy and coefficient of variation (< 20 %)
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PC 28:0	PC O-		
PC 44:0	PC O-		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Reported data quantified with PC 28:0
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

6) FC[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	FC	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	ALEX
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Centroiding, Lock mass correction, Background subtraction
	Fragment name Cholestadiene		
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	multiplexing (MSX, n=2) of FC and the internal standard

6) FC[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Accuracy and coefficient of variation (< 20 %)
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
	Internal standard Fragment(s) Endogenous subclass FC[D7] Cholestadiene[D7] FC		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	multiplexing (MSX, n=2) of FC and the internal standard FC[D7]
Type I isotope correction	Yes		